

6G ✦ REFERENCE

6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing

6G-REFERENCE envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with sustainable solutions that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

6G ✦ REFERENCE will

Develop integrated circuit and antenna component solutions, including dynamic frequency and spatial antenna filtering to enable efficient spectrum coexistence schemes.

Deploy practical hardware enablers in terms of complexity, cost and power consumption that could end up constituting a reference design for future 6G-distributed radios.

Our Challenges

Accurate synchronization among distributed radio units (cell-free deployments)

Fronthaul data distribution

Low complexity/cost/consumption radios

Integration of sensing capabilities

Coexistence with other services

Our Use Cases

Immersive communications

Time sensitive network applications

Integrated sensing and localization

Our Methodology

The project targets **practical integrated circuits (IC) and antenna systems for 6G applications**. 6G-REFERENCE will:

Explore radio system operation in the 10-15GHz range

Develop hardware concepts and show feasibility in CMOS

Use additive manufacturing for antenna arrays and nanotechnology for sensors

Our Partners

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